

Red Blood Cell Indices beyond Haemoglobin Show Limited Utility for Iron Deficiency Detection in Bangladeshi Adult Women: A Tertiary Care Hospital Study

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Abstract

Background: Anaemia in women remains a major health concern in low-income countries like Bangladesh. It puts at risk the well-being of women of childbearing age and hinders progress toward achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030. For treating anemia, injectable iron supplements are inexpensive, efficient, and have a quicker onset of action. However, administering it without confirming iron status may result in iron overload. Although red blood cell (RBC) indices are often used as surrogate markers for iron status, their diagnostic accuracy remains controversial. **Objective:** The goal of our study is to assess whether RBC indices alone can reliably predict iron deficiency, with the aim of reducing the cost of iron profiling and guiding safe parenteral iron supplementation, so that anaemia can be prevented at the root level at an affordable cost. **Methods:** The study included Bangladeshi adult women attending the outpatient department of a tertiary care hospital. After evaluating inclusion and exclusion criteria, patients with clinical anaemia (evidenced by pallor or glossitis) were enrolled. **Results:** Among 130 women, 83 (63.8%) had transferrin saturation or TSAT < 20 %. Haemoglobin (Hb), out of all the complete-blood-count (CBC) indices, showed the strongest correlation with TSAT ($p = 0.55$, $p < 0.001$). Although RBC count and MCV differed modestly between groups, adding these and other indices to Hb did not improve

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discrimination. Cross-validated AUC fell from 0.714 (Hb only) to 0.644 (Hb + four indices). Sensitivity increased marginally, but specificity declined, resulting in more false positives. **Conclusion:** Hb may be adequate for correctly determining iron deficiency in Bangladeshi women. The low price of CBC (about 400 BDT) compared with TSAT assessments (about 1,000-2,200 BDT) makes it a cost-effective initial screening tool. However, biochemical testing (TSAT or ferritin) is still required for diagnostic certainty, especially when iron overload is suspected.

Introduction

Iron deficiency is the leading cause of anaemia worldwide and is especially prevalent among pregnant women in South Asia [1,2]. The prevalence of anemia in Bangladesh is higher among pregnant women (>46%), teenage girls (30%), and non-pregnant women (33%) [3]. Serum ferritin and transferrin saturation (TSAT), the gold standard diagnostic tests for iron deficiency, are not always accessible in areas with limited resources. TSAT, calculated from serum iron and total iron-binding capacity, is considered deficient when < 20 % and overload when > 50 % [4,5].

In Bangladesh, a TSAT (or iron-profile) test costs 1,000–2,200 BDT, whereas a CBC costs only 350–400 BDT [6-8]. If routine tests like CBC indices could reliably predict low TSAT, cost savings and broader screening coverage could be achieved. RBC indices including red blood cell count (RBC count), mean corpuscular haemoglobin (MCH), and mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration (MCHC) are sometimes used to guide parenteral iron therapy in Bangladeshi patients in place of TSAT testing, primarily due to cost constraints, as TSAT investigation costs three times more than that of parenteral iron therapy (BDT 700-1000) itself.

This study evaluates whether haemoglobin (Hb), RBC count, MCV, MCH, and MCHC can substitute for TSAT in detecting iron deficiency among Bangladeshi women.

Materials and Methods:

This single-center study was conducted from November 2024 to April 2025 at Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, a tertiary care hospital in Bangladesh. Total 130 women, aged between 12 and 80 years with clinically apparent anaemia evidenced by pallor and glossitis were enrolled in this cross-sectional study.

Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional Ethics Committee.

After taking informed written consent, known diabetes, hypertension, Malignancy, chronic kidney disease, chronic liver disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, asthma, organ failure, and any other systemic diseases causing anaemia were excluded. Patients who did not provide informed written consent were also excluded. The participants were then assessed for Anaemia and underwent a CBC and biochemical testing for iron status, including serum ferritin, serum iron, total iron-binding capacity (TIBC), and TSAT was calculated. The sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values of RBC indices were calculated using standard diagnostic thresholds.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics and Welch’s t-tests compared iron-deficient (TSAT < 20 %) and iron-adequate (TSAT ≥ 20 %) groups. Spearman correlation assessed monotonic relationships between CBC indices and TSAT. Logistic regression models, using (a) Hb alone and (b) all five CBC indices, were evaluated via five-fold cross-validation using the caret package in R. Model performance metrics included AUC, sensitivity, and specificity. ROC curves were generated for both models.

Results

Descriptive statistics

Women with TSAT < 20 % had, on average, Hb levels ≈ 1.5 g dL⁻¹ lower than those with adequate iron status (p < 0.001) (Table 1). RBC and MCV group means were also modestly lower in the deficient group (RBC: p ≈ 0.015; MCV: p ≈ 0.036), while MCH and MCHC showed no statistically significant differences (MCH p ≈ 0.25; MCHC p ≈ 0.62).

Table 1: Groupwise Comparison of CBC Indices between Women with Low Transferrin Saturation (TSAT < 20 %) and Those with Adequate Iron Status (TSAT ≥ 20 %)

Variable	Deficient (n = 83)	Adequate (n = 47)	p-value
Hb (g dL ⁻¹)	10.10 ± 2.13	11.56 ± 1.33	< 0.001
RBC (10 ¹² L ⁻¹)	4.12 ± 0.60	4.37 ± 0.54	0.0146
MCV (fL)	76.56 ± 12.07	80.78 ± 10.13	0.0359
MCH (pg)	25.75 ± 7.81	31.77 ± 35.09	0.2514
MCHC (g dL ⁻¹)	34.58 ± 30.2	32.95 ± 1.60	0.6245

Note: Values are mean ± SD; p-values from Welch’s two-sample t-test

Correlations with TSAT

Hb had the strongest association with TSAT ($\rho \approx 0.55$, $p \approx 0$), while RBC count had the weakest $\rho \approx 0.23$ (Table

2). Large within-group variability blunts the t-test for MCH and MCHC, yet both indices correlate moderately with iron status across the whole TSAT range (MCH $\rho = 0.40$, MCHC $\rho = 0.51$, both $p < 10^{-5}$).

Table 2: Spearman Rank-Correlation Coefficients (ρ) between TSAT (%) and Individual CBC Variables in the Combined Cohort (n = 130)

Variable	Spearman Rho	p-value
Hb (g dL ⁻¹)	0.550	1.20e-11
RBC (10 ¹² L ⁻¹)	0.231	8.17e-03
MCV (fL)	0.370	1.44e-05
MCH (pg)	0.400	2.47e-06
MCHC (g dL ⁻¹)	0.507	7.76e-10

Note: All correlations are positive; p-values are from exact two-sided tests for $\rho \neq 0$

Predictive performance

Adding extra CBC indices does not improve discrimination (Table 3). Cross-validated AUC falls from 0.714 (Hb only) to 0.644 when RBC, MCV, MCH and MCHC are included. Sensitivity increased slightly with

additional indices, from 0.832 to 0.843, but at the expense of lower specificity (0.342 to 0.273). Thus, the multivariable model added complexity but marginally reduced discrimination and increased false positives, reflecting over-fitting.

Table 3: Cross-Validated Diagnostic Performance for Predicting Low Transferrin Saturation (TSAT < 20 %) from CBC Indices

Model	5-fold CV AUC	Sensitivity	Specificity
Hb only	0.714	0.832	0.342
Hb + RBC + MCV + MCH + MCHC	0.644	0.843	0.273

Note: AUC = area under the receiver-operating-characteristic curve; values are means from 5-fold cross-validation. Sensitivity and specificity correspond to the optimal Youden cut-point within each training fold.

ROC curve

Haemoglobin captures most of the predictive signal available in standard CBC (Figure 1). The near-overlap of apparent AUCs in the two models confirms that Hb alone explains virtually the same proportion of outcome variance as the five-marker panel. Model

optimism, or the tendency of a model to look better on the data it was trained on than it will on new, unseen data, is also evident. Apparent AUCs (~0.72) exceed the cross-validated values (0.64-0.71), reinforcing the need for out-of-sample evaluation when judging potential screening tests.

Figure 1: Receiver-Operating-Characteristic (ROC) Curves for the Multivariate CBC Model (Hb + RBC + MCV + MCH + MCHC) and the Single-Predictor Model Using Haemoglobin (Hb) Alone, Fitted on the Full Datasets. The Diagonal Line Represents Random Classification

Discussion

Our findings highlight the central role of Hb concentration in reflecting iron status among women, with Hb levels approximately 1.5 g dL^{-1} lower in individuals comparable with TSAT below 20%. This difference was statistically significant and clinically meaningful, underscoring Hb's potential utility as a first-line screening marker for iron deficiency. While other CBC indices—including RBC count and MCV also showed modest reductions in the iron-deficient group, their contributions were comparatively smaller and less consistent.

The correlation analyses reinforced this hierarchy. Haemoglobin showed the strongest monotonic association with TSAT (Spearman's $\rho = 0.55$), while RBC count and MCV exhibited weaker correlations. Interestingly, despite large within-group variability and non-significant group-wise differences, both MCH and MCHC correlated moderately with TSAT across the full cohort. This suggests that continuous TSAT variation may be better captured through correlation methods than through dichotomous comparisons alone.

From a diagnostic standpoint, our results suggest that adding additional CBC markers to haemoglobin does not meaningfully improve the ability to discriminate between iron-deficient and iron-replete women. Although the multivariate model picked up slightly more true cases of deficiency (higher sensitivity), it also wrongly labeled more healthy women as deficient (lower specificity). Overall accuracy also decreased as the cross-validated AUC dropped from 0.714 with Hb alone to 0.644 with all markers. Since AUC measures how well the test separates women with and without iron deficiency, the fact that the AUC decreased means the extra markers actually made the test worse. This pattern, alongside the observed gap between apparent and cross-validated AUCs, is consistent with over fitting - a common limitation when building multivariate models from limited sample sizes, where a model learns patterns specific to the sample at hand that do not hold up in other groups [9-11].

These findings align with previous literature suggesting that, while iron deficiency can manifest in altered red cell indices, haemoglobin remains the most robust single marker available within the standard CBC panel [12-14]. Our results also reinforce the notion that complex models do not always translate into better screening tools, particularly when simplicity, interpretability, and out-of-sample performance are prioritized [15].

Implications for Bangladesh

With gestational anaemia prevalence $> 46\%$ and out-of-pocket health expenditure dominant, a tiered approach is pragmatic:

- **Baseline CBC** at first antenatal visit; classify $\text{Hb} < 11 \text{ g dL}$ as probable deficiency and initiate iron supplementation per WHO guidelines.

- **Second-line testing (TSAT)** for women with normal Hb but persistent clinical suspicion, those who fail to respond to supplementation, or contexts where iron overload must be excluded (e.g., haemoglobinopathies clusters).

Parenteral iron for severely deficient group without major known risk factors may be cost effective in terms of cost of TSAT assay, especially for low-income countries like Bangladesh. Such algorithms align with community supplementation programs that have reduced maternal morbidity in rural Bangladesh.

Conclusions

We have observed that haemoglobin alone can identify iron deficiency in at least 83% of cases in our cohort, making it a cost-effective first-line screening tool. This study confirms that routine CBC indices, especially haemoglobin (Hb), can reflect iron deficiency in Bangladeshi women. However, direct biochemical tests (TSAT or ferritin) remain necessary for accurate iron deficiency, and TSAT should be performed in clinical practice to confirm whether iron deficiency or overload is present.

Limitations

Limitations are a modest sample size from a single health facility, absence of inflammatory biomarkers, and potential diurnal variation in serum iron. Selection bias cannot be excluded, and results may not generalize to all adults or other geographic regions.

Future Directions

Larger multi-center cohorts would allow construction of cost-optimized decision trees. Machine-learning approaches with external validation could test whether additional low-cost parameters (red-cell distribution width, reticulocyte Hb content) meaningfully improve predictive accuracy without requiring biochemical assays.

Conflict of Interest

There was no conflict of interest.

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Author Contributions

Concept – SG; Design – SAT, SH, IHD; Supervision – SAT, ZH; Materials – SG, SAT; Data Collection and/or Processing – SG, SAT, MA, MT; Analysis and/or Interpretation – SAT, IHD; Literature Search – SG, SAT; Writing – SG, SAT, IHD; Critical Reviews – SG, ZH,

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